

Do Parental Support and Academic Optimism Predict Curricular Involvement among Students? A study of Secondary School Students in Anambra State

By

Anierobi, Elizabeth Ifeoma

ei.anierobi@unizik.edu.ng

Department of Educational Foundations,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka

Nwasor, Victor Chekume

nwa-principal@unizik.edu.ng

Department of Educational Foundations,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka

Alaribe, Christopher Obinna

co.alaribe@unizik.edu.ng

Department of Educational Foundations,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka

Onyeka, Edith Chinyere

ech.onyeka@unizik.edu.ng

Science Education Department,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka

Abstract

The academic achievement of students in public secondary schools in Anambra State has fluctuated over the years in their external examinations, despite the positive academic outcomes related to students' academic optimism and parental support in their children's education. Students in this area are still caught in a web of factors that prevent them from actively engaging in their studies. This study attempts to determine parental participation and academic optimism as predictors of curricular involvement of secondary school children in Anambra State. The study will be of great benefit in not only advancing the frontiers of knowledge but also in exposing parents to the need to be committed to the academic life of their children. The study adopted a correlational research design to determine the predictive power of parental support and academic optimism on the curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State. The results showed that curricular involvement is positively correlated with parental support and academic optimism. It also demonstrated that parental support and academic optimism work together to enhance secondary school students' curricular involvement in Anambra State. The study's conclusions led to the recommendation that parents should provide the necessary support for the education of their children to boost their optimism and raise their curricular involvement.

Keywords: parental support, academic optimism, curricular involvement, secondary school students

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Introduction

Curriculum exposures would be pointless if students do not get involved in them. Stakeholders in education are therefore concerned about the curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State. Students who do not participate sufficiently in academic activities may suffer crippling effects that affect society generally, in addition to the individual students. For example, low curricular involvement, which raises the risk of low academic performance and failures among students may have a trickle-down effect on lower student literacy and dropout rates (Chika, 2012), which may result in social marginalization. It is expected of secondary school pupils to acquire the knowledge and abilities needed to prepare them for both postsecondary education and a productive life in society. This entails learning about a variety of topics, including science, arithmetic, language arts, social studies, and the arts, in addition to gaining proficiency in important life skills like flexibility, cooperation, and time management (Ozeren, 2023). The secondary education curriculum does this by expanding the knowledge acquired at the primary education level. Therefore, the quality of education youngsters receive should not be viewed as children's playthings to ensure suitable preparedness of these students.

Teachers are responsible for making sure that students are participating actively in their academic work and quickly following directions. Teachers can achieve this by delivering brief lectures to students to bring the lesson back into focus and encourage them to generate ideas for the topic based on their everyday experiences, brainstorming, a group project that fosters cooperation and teaches students to respect one another's viewpoints, group reports that help students learn how to write reports as a way to wrap up group meetings, technology-based exercises that enhance students' ability to study and expand their learning, and PowerPoint presentations that assist students in reviewing material covered in class (Abulhul, 2021). This is given that curricular involvement is a path to academic success. Apart from the roles played by teachers to get students actively involved in curricular experiences, students on their part should show willingness, readiness and interest in taking part in their studies. Students should put in efforts to understand concepts and academic content offered to them, develop the capacity to positively identify with the school and its curricular activities; and engage in overt behaviours such as active class participation. By implication, students must be actively involved in their studies to learn and develop psychomotor abilities for functional living.

However, there are many distractions confronting secondary school students from their studies that they must deal with. For instance, Anierobi, Etodike, Okeke and Ezennaka (2021) maintained that the grip of social media addiction and procrastination are enemies to students' active participation in studies. Some scholars asserted that students are distracted from active involvement in their studies as a result of negative peer influence (Filade, Bello, Uwaoma, Anwanane & Nwangburuka, 2019). However, some scholars aver that students with a high level of academic optimism, self-efficacy and positive psychological capital are likely to take an active part in curricular experiences presented to them (Chikezie, Anozie & Ugwu, 2022). The ripple effect of poor curricular involvement could be observed in poor academic achievement experienced by secondary school students. This is validated by Gegeleso and Ayodele (2023) who reported low academic performance among students in Nigeria. It follows that encouraging students to participate fully in their academic and learning activities makes sense. In carrying out this duty, parents and teachers should collaborate. In other words, parents have a role to play in working with the teachers through providing necessary support towards their children's education.

Parental support involves parents' efforts to meet the education needs of their children. Hasan (2016) avers that parental support involves the efforts and assistance that parents put in towards providing the academic needs of their children. Parents have the responsibility of

ensuring that their children are provided with school materials and receive their support for a smooth academic journey. Parents should provide support to their children's education both at the home front and at the school level. Parental support towards the education of children at home involves providing material, emotional and financial support while at the school level, it entails partnering with teachers towards ensuring that their children actively participate in class activities. Literature proved that children who receive adequate support in their education from their parents have good academic outcomes. For instance, it was reported that parental support indirectly boosts the academic performance of students (Kang, Li, Chen, and Bao, 2024) irrespective of gender (Hasan (2016), course areas and school levels (ATES, 2021). Other scholars construed that parental emotional support for the education of their children has some level of influence on students' attendance at school and psychological capital (Carmona-Halty, Salanova & Schaufeli, 2020). Though, parents differ in their levels of support and involvement in their children's education due to varied socioeconomic backgrounds (Schmid and Garrels, 2021), yet a child's academic behaviour and outcomes could be fostered through the support received from parents. One of such academic behaviours that parental support could build in a child is academic optimism.

Optimism is the belief that good, successful and favourable things will happen now and, in the future, (Luthans in Palos et al, 2023). It may be interpreted as making a positive and constructive assessment of achieving success both now and in the future. According to Yue (2022), when faced with difficult situations, optimistic people typically react positively and overcome them while people with lower levels of optimism find it harder to deal with difficult, stressful, and adverse circumstances. Academic optimism, therefore, is the capacity for students to see the bright side of things and have faith that their academic endeavours will succeed. This implies that optimistic students are those who approach learning with a positive outlook and strive for the best results in all their academic endeavours.

Optimism has been identified with positive academic outcomes. For instance, Hayat et al (2023) found a positive relationship between optimism and academic performance among university students in Iran while Anierobi and Unachukwu (2020) linked it with academic engagement among undergraduate students in a federal university in Nigeria. Moreover, Anierobi, Okeke and Etodike (2021) linked optimism to the academic performance of secondary school students. By this, it is implied that optimistic students have high hopes for their abilities, efforts, and achievements and that these hopes should motivate them to participate in class activities. Consequently, when faced with difficulty in academic tasks, optimistic students with these self-beliefs will always anticipate academic success. In their study, Rezael, Kamiri and Ataei (2023) showed that students' academic optimism was significantly impacted by their academic involvement and academic emotions. Similarly, Veldsman (2018) reported that PsyCap, hope, self-efficacy, optimism, and resilience were positively related to academic engagement. Scholars also discovered that among college instructors, work engagement was highly predicted by both reflective teaching and academic optimism (Li et al, 2023). It may be inferred that optimistic students are more likely to succeed academically because they have faith that, with perseverance and drive, they can conquer any challenging academic situation they encounter. This suggests that optimistic students will be more motivated to participate fully in their studies due to their propensity to overcome challenging academic situations. Moreover, Hassan et al (2023) affirmed that social support and psychological capital are key to the active involvement of students in their studies.

The academic achievement of students in public secondary schools in Anambra State has fluctuated over the years in their external examinations, despite the positive academic outcomes related to students' academic optimism and parental support in their children's education. Students in these schools are still caught in a web of factors that prevent them from actively engaging in their studies. By ascertaining parental participation and academic

optimism as predictors of curricular involvement of secondary school children in Anambra State, this study aimed to fill a vacuum in literature. The study will be of great benefit in not only advancing the frontiers of knowledge but also in exposing parents to the need to be committed to the academic lives of their children.

Research Questions

Three research questions and three hypotheses served as the guide for this study:

1. What relationship does parental support have with the curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State?
2. What relationship does academic optimism have with the curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State?
3. What is the joint contribution of parental support and academic optimism to the curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

Ho₁: Parental support does not significantly predict the curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State.

Ho₂: Academic optimism does not significantly predict the curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State.

Ho₃: Parental support and academic optimism do not significantly predict the curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State.

Method

Research Design

The researchers utilized the correlation research design in this study to fulfil their goals of determining the nature of the correlation that exists between parental support and academic optimism (independent variables) and curricular involvement (outcome variable). To be precise, the field data was analyzed by the researchers using linear regression analysis. This analytical approach was used because it is thought to be suitable for illustrating the changes brought about by the addition of each predictor variable to the outcome variable. In this case, the researchers examined the associations existing between parental support and curricular involvement; academic optimism and curricular involvement; and the joint contribution of parental support and academic optimism on curricular involvement.

Research Participants

Nine hundred and fifty-six (956) senior secondary class 2 (SS2) students were selected from a population of 19,708 students in the 261 public secondary schools in Anambra State using a multi-stage simple random sampling technique. The sample size consisted of 956 SS2 class students (male 47.7%, female 52.3%). The sample characteristics are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Students' Socio-demographic Characteristics

	Mean	SD	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age			-	-
15 years	-	-	313	32.7
16 years	-	-	446	46.6
17 years	-	-	161	16.9
18 years	-	-	36	2.9
Gender				
Male	-	-	456	47.7
Female	-	-	500	52.3
Total	-	-	956	100.0

Source: Field Work (2023)

Table 1 revealed that the sample size consists of more female SS2 students (500, 52,3%) than male SS2 students (456, 47.7%). 313 representing 32.7% of the students are 15 years old; 446 representing 46.6% are 16 years old; 161 respondents representing 16.9 % are 17 years old and 36 participants representing 2.9% are 18 years old.

Ethical/ Consent Consideration

The researchers made sure that the social sciences and education research's accepted ethical norms were adhered to. This was done by getting the respondents' permission and informing them that they could choose to continue with the study or stop it at any time if they felt it was suitable to do so. Since no sensitive student information was gathered, an anonymous data collection process was used. While gathering data, the researchers steered clear of any identifying markers.

Instruments for Data Collection

The Parental Support Questionnaire (PIQ), Academic Optimism Questionnaire (AOQ), and Curricular Involvement Questionnaire (AEQ) are the tools used to collect data for the study. The PSQ, a 15-item measure adapted from Anierobi et al (2023), was utilized in this study using Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1) as the response levels for the items. A respondent's PSQ score might range

from 15 to 60 at its highest point. Consequently, higher parental support is indicated by a score of 30 or above, whereas lower parental support is indicated by a score of less than 30. The Academic Optimism Questionnaire was adopted from Anierobi et al (2021). It is a 5-item tool with a four-point response scale of strongly agree, agree, disagree, and strongly disagree weighted as 4, 3, 2, and 1 correspondingly. Each respondent might receive a maximum score of 16 and a minimum score of 4. The Curricular Involvement Questionnaire (CIQ) for this study is a 20-item instrument designed on a four-point response of Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly Disagree (1). The minimum score for the instrument was 20 while the maximum score was 80. The instrument was adapted from the work of Hart, Stewart and Jimerson (2011). Experts in the field of education validated the three sets of instruments, and the Cronbach Alpha method was used to assess their reliability. The instruments produced alpha coefficients of 0.72, 0.71, and 0.70 for PSQ, AOQ, and CIQ, respectively.

Method of Data Analysis

Using SPSS version 25, data gathered from the respondents were examined using linear regression models. To make sure the items in our data were consistent within, we first vetted them. Utilizing SPSS, the researchers conducted Cronbach Alpha (α) testing to determine the dependability and internal consistency of our instruments. A significance level of 0.005 was used by the researchers to examine the data, and they found that any value less than 0.05 was not significant and any value greater than 0.50 was significant. This decided whether to accept or reject the study's null hypotheses.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between parental support and the curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State?

Table 1: Simple linear regression analysis of the relationship between parental support and curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std Error
1	.468	.219	.211	4.733

Data in Table 1 reveal that the correlation coefficient between parental support and students' curricular involvement is 0.468 with a coefficient of determination of .219. This shows that there is a moderate and positive relationship between parental support and the curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State. This means that parental support helps secondary school students to be better involved in their curricular activities. Besides, the coefficient of determination of 0.219 means that a 21.9% variation in the students' curricular involvement can be a result of their parental support.

Research Question 2: What is the nature of the relationship between academic optimism and the curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State?

Table 2: Simple linear regression analysis of the relationship between academic optimism and curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std Error
1	.427	.205	.197	3.912

Data in Table 2 reveal that the correlation coefficient between academic optimism and students' curricular involvement is 0.427 with a coefficient of determination of .205. This shows that there is a moderate and positive relationship between academic optimism and the curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State. This means that academic optimism helps secondary school students to be better involved in their academic pursuits. Besides, the coefficient of determination of 0.205 means that a 20.5% variation in the students' curricular involvement can be a result of their academic optimism.

Research Question 3: What is the joint contribution of parental support on the prediction of curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State?

Table 3: Model Summary for a joint contribution of parental support and academic optimism on the prediction of curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std Error	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.492	.230	.226	2.03602	2	957	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Academic optimism, Parental support

Data in Table 3 reveal that both parental support and academic optimism contributed positively ($r = .492$) to the curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State with a coefficient of determination of .230. This indicates that 31% variation in students' curricular involvement can be accountable to the joint contribution of their parental support and academic optimism. Therefore, parental support and academic optimism jointly contributed 23% to the curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State.

Hypothesis 1: Parental support does not significantly predict the curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State.

Table 4: Regression on the predictive power of parental support on the curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized	T	Sig.	
	Coefficients		Coefficients			
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	25.306	4.227	5.987	.000	
	Parental support	.443	.081	.468	5.140	.000
	R	.468 ^a			.000	
	R ²	.219			.000	
	F	26.421			.000	

a. Dependent Variable: curricular involvement

Data analysis in Table 4 reveals that the predictive influence of parent support on secondary school students' curricular involvement scores in Anambra State was ascertained at $\beta = .47$, $p < .05$ ($n = 960$). The p-value ($p \leq .000$) is less than 0.05, so the null hypothesis was not accepted. Therefore, parental support significantly predicted the curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State.

Hypothesis 2: Academic optimism does not significantly predict the curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State.

Table 5: Regression on the predictive power of academic optimism on curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State.

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized	T	Sig.	
	Coefficients		Coefficients			
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	23.035	2.079	6.075	.000	
	Academic optimism	.402	.065	.427	4.348	.000
	R	.427			.000	

R ²	.205	.000
F	22.153	.000

a. Dependent Variable: curricular involvement

Data analysis in Table 5 reveals that the predictive influence of academic optimism on secondary school students' curricular involvement scores in Anambra State was ascertained at $\beta = .43$, $p < .05$ ($n = 960$). The p-value ($p \leq .000$) is less than 0.05, so the null hypothesis was not accepted. Therefore, academic optimism significantly predicted curricular involvement among secondary school students in Anambra State.

Hypothesis 3: Parental support and academic optimism do not significantly predict the curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State.

Table 6: Model Summary for Joint Predictive Effects of parental support and academic optimism on curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State.

Model	Unstandardized		Standardize	T	Sig.
	Coefficients		d		
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	23.035	2.079		6.075	.000
1 Academic optimism	.231	.052	.205	3.816	.000
Parental support	.334	.081	.354	4.121	.000
R	.492 ^a				.000
R ²	.230				.000
F	15.203				.000

The result in Table 6 shows that the regression coefficient (R) was .492 while R² was .230. This is an indication that the predictor variables jointly contributed 23% to explain the variances in response and the corresponding $F(2, 957) = 15.203$, is statistically significant ($p < .05$). Therefore, the finding indicates that the presence of parental support and academic optimism would have a higher impact on the curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State. The null hypothesis was, therefore, not accepted. Thus, parental support and academic optimism jointly predicted the curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State.

Discussion

The study sought to find the relationships between the predictor variables (parental support and academic optimism) and the outcome variable (curricular involvement). The findings of this study revealed that parental support has a moderate and positive relationship ($r = 0.468$) with the curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State. The result further revealed that parental support significantly predicted ($p < .05, 0.00$) the curricular involvement of secondary school students. This means that students' involvement in the classroom rises in tandem with increased parental support. Deductively, parents who support their children's education by giving them all the resources and assistance they require will encourage their involvement in the curriculum. This finding aligns with Kang, Li, Chen, and Bao, (2024) who showed that parental support promotes academic engagement of students irrespective of gender (Hasan (2016), course areas and school levels (ATES, 2021). It also corroborates the findings that parental emotional support for the education of their children has some level of influence on students' attendance at school and psychological capital (Carmona-Halty, Salanova & Schaufeli, 2020).

The finding also showed a moderate and positive relationship ($r = 0.427$) between academic optimism and curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State. It further showed that academic optimism significantly ($p < .05, 0.00$) predicted the curricular involvement of secondary school students. This implies that an increase in students' academic optimism brings about an increase in their curricular involvement. This finding corroborates the findings of Hayat et al (2023); Anierobi, Okeke and Etodike (2021), and Anierobi and Unachukwu (2020) who found a positive relationship between optimism and academic performance among students. By this, it is implied that optimistic students have high hopes for their abilities, efforts, and achievements and that these hopes should motivate them to participate in class activities. Consequently, when faced with difficulty in academic tasks, optimistic students with these self-beliefs will always anticipate academic success. The finding also aligns with Rezael, Kamiri and Ataei (2023) who showed that students' academic optimism was significantly impacted by their academic involvement and academic emotions. Moreover, it agrees with Veldsman (2018) who observed that PsyCap, hope, self-efficacy, optimism, and resilience were positively related to the academic engagement of students.

The study further showed that parental support and academic optimism made a positive and joint contribution ($r = .492$) to the curricular involvement of secondary school students in Anambra State. When further tested, the joint contribution made was significant ($p < .05, 0.00$). This implies that when parents provide the necessary support for the education of their children, it may enhance the children's academic optimism. Put differently, students' involvement in the classroom can be significantly increased when there is both academic optimism and parental support. This finding is supported by Hassan et al (2023) who found that social support and psychological capital are key to the active involvement of students in their studies. Parents are to provide social support for their children as they journey through their education ladder.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers concluded that parental support towards the education of their children increases their children's involvement in curricular experiences and contents they are provided within their schools. It was also concluded that academic optimism is necessary for the curricular involvement of Anambra State secondary school students and by extension, of other regions high school students. Besides, the presence

of both parental support and academic optimism in the lives of students will greatly improve students' involvement in learning.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Educational psychologists and school counsellors should work together with school authorities to provide stimulating and enriching learning environments to enable students to get more involved in their learning.
2. Parents should make more efforts to provide necessary financial, emotional and all-round support towards the smooth education of their children. This will go a long way in boosting students' academic optimism and involvement in their academic and classroom activities.

Implications of the Study

The results of this study have important implications for encouraging secondary school students to participate actively in their education. At the secondary school level, students' involvement in the curriculum is greatly enhanced by parental support and optimism. Thus, parents should provide the necessary support for the education of their children to guarantee, encourage, and maintain their commitment to their academic duties. Moreover, students should be encouraged to remain optimistic as they pursue their academic goals.

Limitations of the Study

The generalizability of our findings is limited, despite the importance of our work. Our study may have limitations due to the sole reliance on questionnaires for data collection; future research may need to incorporate the use of interviews as a method of data collection. Besides, the responses from respondents from a particular class set (SS2) alone may not represent a true picture of the general experience of all the senior secondary classes and that of all the secondary school students in Anambra State. Considering the above, caution must be taken when extrapolating the findings of the study.

Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests in the study.

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